

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

UDC 93/94

GANJA IS ON THE WAY OF THE NOMADS. THE WAY OF LIFE, CULTURE AND LIFESTYLE OF NOMADS USING THE MIGRATION ROUTE

Hamzayeva Nurlana Garib*candidate of historical sciences, senior lecturer**Ganja State University (Azerbaijan, Ganja)*

ORCID: 0009-00097296-5681

Introduction. For centuries, Turkic nomadic tribes roamed the vast territories from Central Asia to the Caucasus, constantly inscribing their history into the structure of time. Their way of life and traditions, the emergence of states and the conquest of new lands formed a unique kaleidoscope of culture and influence that left a deep mark on the history of mankind. Turkic nomadic tribes were groups of people who led a nomadic lifestyle, migrated in search of pastures and water for their herds. These tribes lived in vast territories from Central Asia to the Caucasus, and their way of life was closely related to natural conditions. Cattle ranching was the backbone of their economy, and their movement from place to place allowed them to maintain the sustainability of their farm. Each nation and people, throughout their formation and establishment, face certain challenges. The peoples who have emerged from these trials with honor and dignity receive the right to life. History shows that obtaining the right to live is important for children along with the scientific, technical and economic development of the people and the country. Religion, morality, heraldry, justice and all the moral values underlying them are values related to the nation's right to life. By taking these material and spiritual values into unity, the Turkish people came out of the merciless trials of history with honor and gained the right to further prosperity.

Research methods

The following methods were used to study the lifestyle of Turkic nomads: 1. Analysis of literary sources: Including the works of historians and ethnographers such as Aşık Paşazade, Ali Sevim, Erdogan Merçil, Osman Turan Ibrahim Kafesoğlu, Ibn Bibi Beyhaki and, as well as modern studies such as the works of Andrianov and Barfield. 2. Field research: Including observations and interviews with modern descendants of Turkic nomads to understand current practices and traditions. 3. Comparative analysis: The study of various nomadic cultures to identify unique and common features. 4. Archaeological research: The study of artifacts and remnants of nomadic settlements for the reconstruction of their way of life.

The results of the study

Cattle breeding was the basis of the economy of the Turkic nomads. Their way of life depended on seasonal movements in search of pastures and water for their flocks. In summer, the nomads moved to cool mountain pastures, and in winter to warm gorges. This lifestyle allowed them to maintain the stability of their herds and provide their family with everything they needed. The main types of livestock bred by Turkic nomads were sheep, goats, horses, camels and cattle. Each type of cattle played an important role in the life and economy of the tribes. Both of us and each of us were students of Molokov, Mesom, Furst and the Turks, because of whom they started their lives, headscarves and other types of business (Sevim and Merchil, 1995). Horses were used for riding and transporting goods, which allowed the nomads to move efficiently over long distances. Camels, due to their endurance, were indispensable in desert and semi-desert areas where other types of livestock could not survive. Cattle breeding required a lot of experience and knowledge about

natural conditions, pastures and water sources. The nomads carefully monitored the condition of their herds, regularly changed pastures to avoid land depletion and provide fresh grass for the animals. This allowed them to maintain a high level of productivity and avoid exotics that could improve the state of the state (Turan, 1969). In winter, when the pastures were covered with snow and the temperature dropped, the nomads headed to warmer gorges and valleys, where green pastures and access to water were preserved. In summer, on the contrary, they moved to mountainous areas where the climate was cooler and there were rich grasses. This lifestyle required high mobility and the ability to quickly adapt to changing environmental conditions. Cattle breeding also influenced the social structure and economic activities of the tribes. The men were mainly engaged in pastures and protecting herds from predators and enemy raids. Women have played an important role in the development of livestock products: they created cheese and casheer from milk, fabric and felt, as well as other products. — expectation and love (Andrianov, 1985). This contributed to the stability of the nomads' economic system and allowed them to create food reserves in case of unforeseen circumstances. Trade was another important component of the economy of the Turkic nomads. They exchanged surplus livestock products for grain, textiles, metals and other goods that they could not produce themselves. Nomadic trade caravans played an important role in spreading cultural and technological advances between different regions of Eurasia (Beyhaki, 1954). This contributed to the development of economic ties and mutual understanding between the peoples. Thus, cattle breeding was not only the main source of livelihood for the Turkic nomads, but also determined their way of life, the structure of society and interaction with the outside world. Their

ability to effectively use natural resources, adapt to changes and maintain the stability of their farms was the key to their survival and prosperity in difficult conditions of nomadic life. The social structure of nomadic tribes was based on kinship ties and traditional customs. The head of the tribe was a man who led the tribe and made important decisions. The elders of the tribe served as advisers, helping in public affairs. Important decisions were made at a general meeting where every adult male had the right to vote. The adoption of Islam had a significant impact on the Turkic nomadic tribes. They began migrating with the Seljuks in the 8th and 10th centuries. The movement of the Turkic tribes passed through Transoxiana, Khorezm, Khorasan and further West. They strengthened their positions in Khorasan and created their own state. Despite the fact that he was led by Sultan Toghrul-Bek, they continued to move westward, reaching the territories of Iran, Iraq and Azerbaijan (Sevim and Merchil, 1995). Turks already lived on the territory of Azerbaijan, some of whom were nomads, while others were sedentary residents of towns and villages. In particular, the city of Ganja has played an important role in this region. At the time of the arrival of the Seljuks, Ganja was one of the border areas adjacent to Byzantium and Georgia. Therefore, Sultan Toghrul Bey deliberately placed Turkish nomads near Ganja in order to strengthen the borders and protect the territory (Turan, 1969). Ganja, located in the western part of modern Azerbaijan, was one of the main cities where important trade and military roads intersected. Its strategic location and role in historical events make it an important center for the development of the region and the understanding of Turkish statehood. The placement of Ganja as a border city made it possible to control the movement of troops and convoys, ensure the security of the territory, and serve as a barrier against possible raids by the Byzantines and Georgians. As an example, we can cite the war that took place in 1045 between the army of nomads under the leadership of Kutalman Bey and the Georgian king Liparid, who, at the suggestion of the Byzantine operator, was Seljuks (Ibni Bibi, 1954). Ganja was also an important trade center, through which the caravan routes connecting East and West passed. This made it an economically important city, which promoted the development of trade, the exchange of cultural and technological achievements. Ganja attracted merchants and artisans from all over the world, which contributed to its prosperity and growth. At a certain stage in its history, Ganja became the capital of the Seljuk state, which emphasized its political and military importance. The Seljuks chose Ganja as their capital because of its strategic location and developed infrastructure. The location of the capital in Ganja allowed the Seljuks to effectively manage their territory, maintain communication with various parts of their state and control important trade routes. Ganja served as an administrator and cultural consultant, he controlled the activities and influence of the Seljuk authorities (Sevim and Merchil, 1995). The social structure and culture play an important role in the formation of the people. Therefore, it is necessary to emphasize that the social structure of nomadic tribes

was based on kinship ties and traditional customs. Nomadic tribes had their own culture and way of life. In summer they were moved to cool mountain pastures, and in winter to warm gorges. The nomads' clothes were practical and suited their living conditions. Men wore long dresses and trousers, while women wore long dresses and scarves. The clothes of the Turkic nomads adapted to their lifestyle and climatic conditions. Men wore long dresses, trousers and belts, which provided freedom of movement and protection from wind and sun. Women wore long dresses, shawls and woolen scarves. One of them was made of natural materials, so somehow it turned out that it was easy and fast (Andrianov, 1985). The yurt was the main dwelling of the Turkic nomads, a symbol of their culture and way of life. It was a round portable tent that was easy to disassemble and assemble, and it was ideal for a nomadic lifestyle. Yurts were built from a wooden frame covered with felt and sometimes fabric. Felt was created from people who make it simple and warm, living away from winter and hot summers (Turan, 1969). The yurt was based on a wooden frame consisting of masonry (karage), an upper ring (Tunduk) and wooden beams (uuki) that connected the grid to the upper ring. The outer covering of the yurt was made of several layers of felt, which provided thermal insulation and protection from wind and rain. Felt was often decorated with patterns that had symbolic meaning and reflected the cultural traditions of the tribe. The gates of the yurt (yoshik) were usually located on the south side and were made of wood or felt. It can be decorated with carvings or fabric applications (Beyhaki, 1954). The interior of the yurt was simple but functional. There was a fireplace in the center of the house, which was used for cooking and heating the house. Mats and pillows were placed around the hearth, which served for sitting and sleeping. Drawers and chests were used to store clothes, dishes and other items. It is worth noting that everything in the yurt had its place, which helped to maintain order and comfort in a limited space (Andrianov, 1985). The daily life of the Turkish nomads was closely connected with nature and depended on the changing seasons. The men were engaged in cattle breeding, hunting and protection of the tribe. Women were engaged in household chores, cooking, raising children, making felt for yurts and clothes (Turan, 1969). Carpet weaving occupied an important place in the life of the Turkish nomads and was one of the most common forms of art among women. Carpet making required skills and a lot of patience, and the process often began with breeding and shearing sheep to get their wool. Wool was processed, spun and dyed with natural dyes derived from plants, minerals and insects. Turkish carpets had different patterns and colors, each of which had its own symbolic meaning. Geometric patterns, floral motifs and animal images decorated the carpets, turning them into a unique piece of art. Carpets were used not only as a floor covering, but also as walls of the yurt, blankets and household items. Carpet weaving has been passed down from generation to generation, and every woman has contributed to the development of this art (Andrianov, 1985). Apart from pastoral care and hunting,

Turkmen men also played an important role in protecting their tribe. They were soldiers and were called the Alps. The Alps were brave warriors, ready to defend their tribes and native lands at any moment. Since childhood, boys have been taught martial arts. They acquired the skills of horseback riding, archery, and the use of swords and spears. Military training also included strategic thinking and the ability to act as part of a group. The Alps were known for their endurance, bravery and loyalty to their tribes. In battle, they were distinguished by their organization and efficiency, which made them a formidable opponent (Beyhaki, 1954). The Alps played a key role in protecting nomadic tribes from external threats and maintaining discipline within the tribe. They participated in campaigns and military campaigns, guarded caravans and pastures, and participated in diplomatic missions. In peacetime, the Alpines were engaged in training young warriors and maintaining the military readiness of the tribe (Sevim and Merçil, 1995). The Turkish Alps used various techniques and tactics. They were well armed with bows, spears, swords and shields. The main type of equipment was chain mail or leather armor, which provided protection and maneuverability. Horses played an important role in the life of the Alps, providing fast movement and maneuverability in battle. The tactics of the Turkish warriors consisted in using cunning and surprise attacks. They were masters of ambushes and surprise attacks, which allowed them to effectively fight against superior enemy forces. The organization and discipline of the Alpine troops made them an effective fighting force (Beyhaki, 1954). Due to their lifestyle and military training, Turkish nomads have always played a key role in the defense and expansion of the Turkic states. Possessing unique military abilities, nomads were often stationed on the borders of the state, where they performed two important tasks. The first mission of the nomads was to guard the borders. Being excellent warriors, the Alpines reacted quickly to external threats, protecting the territory from enemy invasion. Due to their lifestyle and military training, Turkish nomads have always played a key role in the defense and expansion of the Turkic states. Possessing unique military abilities, nomads were often stationed on the borders of the state, where they performed two important tasks. The first mission of the nomads was to guard the borders. Being excellent warriors, the Alpines reacted quickly to external threats, protecting the territory from enemy invasion. Their mobility and ability to move quickly made it possible to effectively resist attacks and ensure mobility and ability to move quickly made it possible to effectively resist attacks and ensure the security of border areas (Sevim and Merçil, 1995). The second mission of the nomads was to carry out raids (akyns) and looting (yamma) on the territory of weakened neighboring states. These raids not only weakened the enemy, but also allowed them to bring significant material wealth to the Turkish lands. The nomads' military tactics, including surprise attacks and the use of stealth, led them to successfully carry out such operations (Turan, 1969). The life and way of life of the nomads were gradually passed from mouth to mouth and reflected in folklore works. Among them,

the heroic epic "Kitabi Dede Gorgud" can be noted — epic poems that played an important role in the cultural heritage of the Turkic nomads. They talked about the exploits and adventures of the heroes, passed wisdom and guidance from generation to generation. Epics were not only entertainment, but also a means of conveying the values and history of the tribe (Aşık Paşazade, 2000). Kita Kitabi Dede Gorgud presented various stories about battles, love, friendship and loyalty. They reflected the life values and worldview of the nomads, their attitude to nature, family and society. These poems not only charmed listeners with their amazing stories, but also inspired them to heroism and self-sacrifice. The epics of Dede Gorgud were an integral part of the culture and lifestyle of the Turkic nomads. They served not only as a source of entertainment, but also as a means of education and upbringing. Thanks to these epics, the nomads preserved their history, traditions and culture, passing them on from generation to generation (Andrianov, 1985). Today, the epic "Kitabi Dede Gorgud" is not only a literary work, but also the key to understanding the culture and spiritual life of the Turkic nomads. It reflects the worldview, values and ideals of nomadic tribes, which makes it an incredibly valuable resource for studying the history and culture of this amazing people (Aşık Paşazade, 2000). Conclusions: The presence of nomadic tribes near Ganja had a significant impact on the region. First, they strengthened the borders, ensuring the security of the territory. The placement of nomads near the borderlands created a buffer zone, making the territory less vulnerable to attacks and invasions. In addition, the nomads contributed to the economy of the region. Their presence contributed to the development of animal husbandry and crafts. Trade with nomads also facilitated the development of markets and the exchange of goods (Sevim and Merçil, 1995). The cultural influence of the nomads was also significant. They brought their traditions, music and art, which enriched the cultural heritage of the region. In addition, nomads often exchanged knowledge and experience with the indigenous population, encouraged cultural exchanges and united various ethnic groups (Beyhaki, 1954). At the beginning of the 13th century, the migration of nomads together with the Mongol invasions caused significant changes in the region. Under pressure from the Mongol armies, Turkish nomads began migrating west to safer areas. They passed through Anatolia and headed with the Ottomans to Eastern Europe and the Balkans. However, in the XVI century, under the influence of the Safavid Shah Ismail Khatai, some nomadic tribes returned from Anatolia to the territory of Azerbaijan, and over time almost all nomads switched to a sedentary lifestyle (Sevim and Merçil, 1995). Conclusion Turkic nomadic tribes remain an endless source of inspiration and wonder. Their spirit of wandering and adventure, wisdom and cultural heritage continue to live in the hearts of people and on the

pages of history. Studying their history, we are inspired by the strength and resilience of these peoples, their ability to adapt to change and their desire for freedom. Turkish nomads have left their mark on the sands of time, and their history will live forever, reminding of the greatness of the human spirit. These peoples not only survived in harsh conditions, but also created unique cultural and artistic works that continue to delight researchers and history buffs. Their contribution to the development of architecture, literature and art cannot be overestimated. Great poets and architects such as Nizami and Ajemi left behind a legacy that is still admired and respected today. In addition, their political and military strategies, their ability to build alliances and find diplomatic solutions in difficult situations indicate a high level of their organization and wisdom. The Mongol invasion could wipe them off the face of the earth, but the Kipchaks managed to preserve their identity, adapt to new conditions and even contribute to the formation of new states and cultures. Thus, the Turkic nomadic tribes are a living example of how perseverance, wisdom and love of freedom can overcome any obstacles and leave an indelible mark on the history of mankind. Their legacy inspires us to preserve and study their culture in order to pass on to the next generations all the power and greatness of these great peoples.

References

1. Andrianov, B. V. (1985) **Neosedloe naselenie mira**. Moskva: Nauka.
2. Aşık Paşazade (2000) **Garîb-nâme**. Ankara: Türk Tarih Kurumu.
3. Barfield, T. J. (1989) **Opasnaya granitsa: kochevye imperii i Kitay (221 g. do n. e. — 1757 g. n. e.)**. Stanford: Stanford University Press.
4. Barthold, V. V. (1968) **Four Studies on the History of Central Asia**. Leiden: Brill.
5. Beyhaki (1954) **Tarihi Mesudi**. Tehran: Babayan.
6. Bosworth, C. E. (1968) **The Ghaznavids: Their Empire in Afghanistan and Eastern Iran 994-1040**. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press.
7. Boyle, J. A. (1977) **The Cambridge History of Iran: Volume 5, The Saljuq and Mongol Periods**. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
8. Frye, R. N. (1975) **The Golden Age of Persia**. London: Weidenfeld & Nicolson.
9. Golden, P. B. (1992) **An Introduction to the History of the Turkic Peoples**. Wiesbaden: Otto Harrassowitz.
10. İbni Bibi (1954) **Selcukname**. Ankara: Türk Tarih Kurumu.
11. Kafesoğlu, İ. (1996) **Selçuklular Tarihi**. Ankara: Türk Tarih Kurumu.
12. Lamb, H. (2003) **Genghis Khan: Emperor of All Men**. New York: Bantam.
13. Morgan, D. (2007) **The Mongols**. Oxford: Blackwell.
14. Sevim, A. and Merçil, E. (1995) **Selçuklu Devleti Tarihi**. İstanbul: Dergah Yayınları.
15. Sinor, D. (1990) **The Cambridge History of Early Inner Asia**. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
16. Turan, O. (1969) **Selçuklular Tarihi ve Türk – İslam Medeniyeti**. İstanbul: İstanbul Üniversitesi Edebiyat Fakültesi.